

DETECTION OF OBSESSIVE – COMPULSIVE DISORDER IN ADOLESCENTS ACCORDING TO THE CATEGORIES

Khudaiberdieva Dilorom Khaidar kizi

Doctoral student of Gulistan State University

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Abstract: In this article is observed how to recognize obsessive – compulsive disorder among other psychological disorders, and detection according to the types.

Key words: obsessive-compulsive disorder, behavior, mental, neurosis, compulsion, symptoms, psychological disorders, purification, symmetry, taboo thoughts, harmful, hoarding.

Obsessive – compulsive disorder (OCD) is characterized by repeated obsessive thoughts, images, impulses or ideas (obsessions), usually causing anxiety or distress (distress), or recurring ideational (mental) or behavioral phenomena (compulsions), accompanied by a feeling of need to fulfill them either in accordance with obsessions, or according to certain rules that must be followed in order to achieving a feeling of “action completion”.

There are described various options for the content of obsessions and rituals. Nevertheless, among them can be distinguished the following categories (“symptomatic dimensions”).

“Purification” – fears associated with contamination/contamination and cleansing rituals

“Symmetry” – obsessions about symmetry and rituals of repeating, “correct” performing actions, arranging objects in a certain order and counting

“Taboo thoughts” - examples include aggressive, sexual, blasphemous obsessions and related compulsions

“Harmful” – such as thoughts or ideas about causing harm to oneself or to someone else (“contrasting obsessions”) and re-checking rituals (“re-control”) regarding this matter.

“Hoarding” – obsessions and compulsions about collecting and accumulating various items.

For detection the obsessive – compulsive disorder was chosen adolescents from Mirzaabad district ages between 10 -16. According to the research was detected such kind of signs of obsessive – compulsive disorder in children, which appear in the form of compulsions, include:

- ✓ change of mood;
- ✓ over eating;
- ✓ desire for symmetry;
- ✓ excessive passion for any type of activity;
- ✓ senseless counting of objects on the street, steps or cracks in the asphalt.

Pic 1. OCD signs

From the gained results we can understand that 47% percent of respondents have the signs connected with changing mood. 6% percent of adolescents have problems with over eating, but they do not have problems with obesity. 21 % percent of respondents pay attention to the order of things. 12 % percent have excessive passion for any type of activity (the child cuts, sculpts, draws and cannot stop), it was more recognizable in adolescents at the age between 11 – 13. 14 % percent of the respondents said that they count objects senseless.

For sure, not all this category can be recognized as a symptom of obsessive – compulsive disorder. In some cases, they can be distinguished as a normal habit. But even habits should be at the edge of consciousness. And for getting more concrete result it demands further research.

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